

THE EFFECT OF METAL LAYER THICKNESS ON ENERGY ABSORPTION DURING FRACTURE OF METAL/CERAMIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The metal layer thickness in multi-layered aluminium/alumina composites has been varied in order to examine its effect on the failure behaviour during crack propagation normal to the plane of the layers. The failure mode changed from single to multiple cracking of the ceramic layers as the thickness of the metal layers was increased. Experimental results have shown a corresponding trend of increasing energy absorption. These are in good agreement with predictions from a simple model for energy absorption in these materials.

INTRODUCTION

In metal/ceramic multi-layered composites, the thickness of the metal layer relative to that of the ceramic has been shown to exert a dominant effect on the fracture behaviour[1, 2]. Specifically, when the layer thickness of the metal is low relative to that of the ceramic, fracture of the composite tends to occur by the propagation of a single dominant crack. When the ratio is high, fracture involves multiple cracking of each brittle layer. There has, however, been very little quantitative study of the fracture energy of notched or unnotched multi-layers that exhibit either type of behaviour. In the present study, the fracture energy of aluminium/alumina laminates was measured and compared with predictions from a simple model.

EXPERIMENTAL

SPECIMEN PRODUCTION

Multi-layered composites consisting of six layers of 99.0% aluminium (Advent, U.K.) and seven layers of 99.5% alumina (Hybrid Laser Tech, UK), were produced by vacuum diffusion bonding. The alumina substrates had a density of 3.82 Mg m⁻³ and a Weibull modulus[3] of 16. During processing, the temperature was 650°C, the chamber pressure was ~ 10⁻⁵ Torr, and the bonding pressure of 8 MPa was maintained for four hours. Specimens produced in this way exhibited strong interfacial bonding; evidence of this is apparent in Fig. 1.

Specimen dimensions are presented in Table 1. After cutting, one side surface was polished to a 1 µm finish in order to observe the failure mechanisms. Some of the specimens were notched prior to testing using a diamond blade of 200 µm thickness, with the notch tip extending to the second ceramic layer.

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of the fracture surface from specimen B, revealing a strong interfacial bond.

Specimen Code	Metal Layer Thickness, h_m (mm)	Ceramic Layer Thickness, h_c (mm)	Number of Ceramic Layers, n	Specimen Width, b (mm)	Roller Span, Inner, Outer (mm)
A	0.05	0.5	7	6.2	35, 60
B	0.32	0.5	7	7.2	40, 80
C	0.92	0.5	7	8.2	40, 80

Table 1. Specimen and testing dimensions

MECHANICAL TESTING

Testing was carried out using an ESH 10 kN universal testing machine, under four-point bending configuration (Fig. 2). The tests were carried out under displacement control and data logged with a MacLab data acquisition system on a Macintosh. A floating platen system[4] was used to distribute the applied load equally between the rollers. During the tests, photographs were taken of the specimen side surface using a 35 mm Nikon camera.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The stress and strain fields surrounding cracks in the ceramic layers were investigated by finite element modelling, carried out on a Silicon Graphics Indy Workstation using Abaqus software. The analyses were conducted using plane strain conditions and a mixture of 8-noded quadrilateral and 6-noded triangular elements. Large deformation analyses with hybrid elements were used, with perfect bonding between the layers. The modelling was based on a single cracked ceramic layer, with a crack tip that extended into the metal layer a distance of $h_m/40$ from the metal/ceramic interface, with a crack tip radius of $h_m/40$. This choice of crack tip geometry has been found[5] to give good agreement with experimental results for crack tip strain fields by comparison with results from moiré interferometry experiments. The remaining ceramic layers in the model were uncracked.

Figure 2. Four-point bend test set-up.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3. Load-displacement plots for the three specimens. The recorded peak loads, P_{\max} , for specimens A, B and C were 427, 465 and 1290 N respectively.

BEND TEST RESULTS

All of the specimens failed by successive formation of cracks in the ceramic layers. Load-displacement curves for the three specimens (A, B and C) are shown in Fig.3. The loads plotted in this figure have been normalized by the peak load, P_{\max} , sustained by the specimen

concerned. Similar plots were obtained for corresponding unnotched specimens. The stress in the outer ceramic layer when it cracked was similar for the three specimens, at about 150 to 200 MPa for the notched cases and 200 to 300 MPa for the unnotched cases. The micrographs presented in Fig.4, however, show that the fracture modes differed for the different metal thickness levels. Specimens with *thinner* metal layers (A and B) failed by the propagation of a *single* crack. No further increase in load was required to propagate cracks once initial crack growth commenced. In the case of *thick* metal layers (specimen C), however, a *multiple* cracking fracture pattern was observed, such that additional cracks formed within each ceramic layer with increasing load, following an initial load drop.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs from the sides of surfaces of (a) specimen B and (b) specimen C

The nominal fracture energy, G_{exp} , was estimated from experimental plots of load, P , against displacement, z

$$G_{exp} = \frac{1}{A} \int P dz \quad (1)$$

in which A is the nominal crack area. An increase in energy absorption with metal layer thickness was observed. This trend was apparent in both notched and unnotched specimens.

MODELLING OF ENERGY ABSORPTION

Inspection of the side surfaces of the beams suggested that plastic deformation of a metal layer occurred initially (prior to cracking of the ceramic layer beyond the metal layer concerned) within a large zone extending some distance from the crack plane. Subsequently (after cracking of the next ceramic layer), plastic flow in the metal layer became localised in the ligament bridging the two halves of the fractured ceramic layers. This is illustrated schematically in Fig.5.

Based on this experimental observation, the fracture energy was evaluated by estimating the contributions (ΔG_p , ΔG_b) from deformation in these zones (plastic and bridging) to the total fracture energy, G_{tot}

$$G_{tot} = \Delta G_p + \Delta G_b + \Delta G_c \quad (2)$$

The first term, ΔG_p , is the energy dissipated within the large plastic zone surrounding an isolated crack in a brittle layer. This represents the work done within the plastic zone prior to the formation of cracks in adjoining ceramic layers. The second term, ΔG_b , arises from the more intense plastic deformation that subsequently takes place within a smaller volume of metal (a bridging ligament) situated between two cracks in adjoining ceramic layers. The third term is the contribution from fracture of the ceramic layers.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of the two zones in which plastic deformation occurs within the metallic layers during fracture.

The work done within the plastic zone, ΔG_p , is given by

$$\Delta G_p = \frac{1}{A} \int \int \sigma_y d\epsilon_p dV \quad (3)$$

where σ_y is the metal yield stress, $d\epsilon_p$ is an incremental plastic strain, dV is an incremental volume of the plastic zone and A is the fracture area. The metal is assumed to deform in an elastic-perfectly plastic (non-work hardening) manner. The value of ΔG_p was calculated from the results of the finite element analysis in the following way. Firstly, a remote load was applied to the model until the maximum stress in the intact ceramic layer closest to the cracked ceramic layer reached 400 MPa. This value was chosen for the mean ceramic strength on the basis of experimental measurements[3]. The work done within the plastic zone in the metal was obtained by numerically integrating the incremental plastic work over the entire volume of the plastic zone, up to that point. This computation was carried out separately for the three metal layer thicknesses examined experimentally. In order to plot ΔG_p as a function of metal content, a polynomial was fitted to these three data points - see below. (In practice, any error

from this procedure is of little significance, since the contribution from this source turns out to be relatively small.)

The energy dissipated during deformation of the metal bridging layer, ΔG_b , was estimated using a simple analytical treatment. In developing such a treatment, account must be taken of the constraint on metal deformation imposed by the presence of the ceramic layers. Using results from previous investigation[6] of this problem, the work done in the bridging ligament can be written

$$\Delta G_b = \int \frac{h_m b \sigma(u)}{(h_m + h_c) b} du = f \int \sigma(u) du \quad (4)$$

where u is the crack-opening displacement (see Fig.5), f is the metal volume fraction, $\sigma(u)$ is the bridging stress in the metal layer acting on the crack faces at the crack plane, b is the specimen width and u is the average crack opening of the metal layer. The value of $\sigma(u)$ is affected by the degree of constraint exerted by the presence of the adjoining ceramic layers[2, 6, 7]. Account is taken of this effect by the introduction of a factor, α , by which the stress is increased relative to the yield stress of the metal in uniaxial tension, σ_y . Furthermore, the bridging stress falls as the crack opening displacement increases and the severity of this constraint is reduced. It has been shown[8] that a linear change can be approximated, so the following expression was used for the bridging stress in the current work:

$$\sigma(u) = \alpha \sigma_y \left(1 - \frac{u}{u_c} \right) \quad (5)$$

where u_c is the critical crack opening at which the bridging stress reaches zero (ligament failure). In the present case, it may be assumed[9] that $u_c \sim h_m$. The value of the constraint factor, α , was taken to be 2, broadly in line with previous analyses[2, 6, 7] of this effect. The yield stress for the (commercial purity) aluminium used in the current work was 50 MPa.

The final expression needed in eqn.(2) is that for the contribution from fracture of the ceramic, ΔG_c . This may be written as

$$\Delta G_c = \frac{h_c b G_c}{(h_m + h_c) b} = G_c (1 - f) \quad (6)$$

where G_c is the fracture energy of the ceramic. The value of this was taken as 40 J m^{-2} , in line with previous measurements[10] made on similar material.

The three contributions to the total fracture energy, G_{tot} , are plotted in Fig.6 as a function of the metal volume fraction. Also shown on this plot are the experimental values obtained from the load-displacement data for the three specimens listed in Table 1. The data for ΔG_b and ΔG_c were obtained from eqns.(4) and (6) respectively. The data for ΔG_p correspond to a quadratic equation fitted to the results from three computations made with the finite element model,

$$\Delta G_p = m_0 + m_1 f + m_2 f^2 \quad (7)$$

The coefficients, m_0 , m_1 and m_2 , in this equation were found to have values of -0.03, 0.97 and -0.47 kJ m^{-2} respectively. These gave good agreement with the three ΔG_p values from the finite element calculations.

Good agreement is apparent in Fig.6 between theory and experiment, even though the modelling is based on propagation of a single dominant crack, whereas in practice multiple cracking was observed with the thicker metal layers. It is also apparent that it is the contribution from the straining of the bridging ligaments which dominates the work done, except for very low metal contents. It seems likely that the expression used for this work represents an over-estimate, at least when the metal layers are relatively thick. The most probable source of this error is that the value of u_c should be less than h_m when h_m is relatively large. For example, cavitation within the bridging ligament would tend to allow it to fail at reduced crack opening displacements and this becomes more likely as the thickness of the metal layers is increased. This area is currently the subject of further work.

Figure 6. Plot of the contributions to the fracture energy as a function of metal volume fraction, together with experimental data for the total fracture energy.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A study has been made of the trend for an increase in energy absorption during failure of metal/ceramic layered systems as the relative thickness of the metal layers is increased. This energy has been measured experimentally during 4-point bending of aluminium / alumina laminates and analysed theoretically in terms of the contributions from plastic flow of the metal

and from fracture of the ceramic. Simple analytical expressions were obtained for each of the contributions to the work of fracture, although the term representing the plastic deformation in a metal layer while only one of its neighbouring ceramic layers is cracked was obtained by curve fitting to data from finite element computations. The analysis indicates that, except at very low metal contents, the fracture energy is dominated by the work done in stretching the bridging ligaments of metal between pairs of fractured ceramic layers. Good agreement has been observed between theory and experiment. However, the analysis is based on the propagation of a single dominant crack. While this is indeed observed with relatively thin metallic layers, there is a transition to multiple cracking of the ceramic layers when the metal layers are relatively thick. Under these circumstances, predictions from the model would be expected to underestimate the work of fracture. This suggests that the analysis is in error for the case of thick metal layers. The most likely source of this error lies in the assumption that the bridging ligaments are stretched until the crack opening displacement is equal to the metal layer thickness. This may be an over-estimate when the metal layers are thick and therefore likely to exhibit internal cavitation. This area is the subject of further work.

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